

INFLUENCE OF MEDIA OWNERSHIP PATTERNS ON GOOD GOVERNANCE IN ENUGU STATE

Mbah Everest Ikechukwu

Abstract

The study examined the influence of media ownership patterns on good governance in Enugu state. The main objective of the study is to assess the influence of media ownership patterns on good governance in Enugu state. The specific objectives of the study are to ascertain the relationship between media ownership and good governance; determine the extent to which the media serve as tools for promoting good governance in Enugu state; examine the relationship between media ownership and media content; and evaluate the relationship between government regulation of the media and good governance. The study was anchored on the Social Responsibility theory and the Gatekeeping theory. The researcher adopted the survey research method for the execution of the study, while adopting the descriptive research design for the study. The population of this study is 344, which came from the selected media houses: FRCN, ESBS, and Dream FM. Since the population size is small and manageable, same figure served as the sample size. The researcher adopted a census sampling technique due to the small and manageable nature of the population figure. The researcher used questionnaire as the research instrument. The researcher employed the content validity. The researcher adopted the Test-Retest Method for the study. Both primary and secondary methods of data were used in this research work for gathering information. The data were presented in table and analyzed with SPSS; the hypotheses were tested by the use of Spearman's Rank Correlation formula. Findings among others revealed that, there are policies that exist in both the public and privately owned media on good governance. The researcher recommended amongst others that there is need for total press freedom considering the fact that there is a significant relationship between media ownership and good governance.

Introduction

According to Paulson (2019), the term "media" refers to a large-scale communication system that reaches and involves almost every member of a community to varying degrees. The word "media" is the plural of "medium," which denotes a conduit or means of transmission. To put it another way, mass media—mainly print and electronic media—are avenues for communication in contemporary society. Providing information to millions of people is the main purpose of the mass media system. The influence of the mass media is enormous. It is assumed that every media outlet has a unique impact on people's attitudes and actions. They can affect the society and vice versa. Even the most remote parts of the world may receive information thanks to the vital communication tool known as the mass media. By assisting us in overcoming the limitations of time and location, they allow us to communicate with one another. They serve society in both primary and secondary capacities (Imbul, 2014).

According to Adelabu and Ikuesewo (2021), the media play a crucial role in governance as a watchdog and a collaborator with other branches of government, making them an essential growth agent in any country. The mass media has played a crucial role in delivering and solidifying the current democratic experience in a developing nation like Nigeria. People can equally engage in the proposal, creation, and formulation of laws in a democracy, either directly or through elected representatives. Reaching big audiences is the primary goal of mass media. The platforms that mass media most commonly use are newspapers, magazines, radio, television, and the internet (Oparaugo, 2021). Apart from these functions, the mass media also encourages social mobilization while providing entertainment, information, and education. In other words, the media as a whole is a powerful informational resource that influences every

aspect of society. They can disseminate knowledge about topics, ideas, and products (Omeje, Oparaugo, & Chukwuka, 2021).

In 1994, Ray Power FM became Nigeria's first privately-owned radio station to broadcast when the military dictatorship deregulated the broadcast industry (Amos & Joseph, 2023). The British Broadcasting Corporation's (BBC) Empire Service was established in 1933, marking the beginning of Nigeria's radio broadcasting history. Since then, the industry has experienced gradual but steady growth. The National Broadcasting Commission rules of 2004, or CAP 11, were deregulated by General Ibrahim Babangida's government in 1992 through Decree 38, which was later amended into Act 55 of 1999. Over the following 20 years, the number of privately owned radio stations in Nigeria increased dramatically as a result of this deregulation (Amos & Joseph, 2023).

The ownership of the broadcast medium is in charge of its general administration and day-to-day operations. Ownership finances the company, invests in it, obtains a license to operate, and renews the license on a yearly basis as needed. Privately held media are thought to be pursuing objectives motivated by a desire to make money, albeit this isn't always the case. The government does not necessarily have total influence over the channels and content, even though it does own a share of the media. If these channels are not subsidized, they usually have to make money, which suggests some degree of autonomy from the government's ideological objectives. The main management and daily operations of the broadcast medium are under the control of its owner. Ownership finances the business, makes investments in it, secures an operating license, and, if necessary, renews the license annually.

The FRCN Enugu is a publicly financed radio broadcasting company in Nigeria. FRCN is thought to have a key role in society's overall evolution. This suggests that FRCN is important when it comes to power dynamics and determining how much power affects people, either favorably or unfavorably. It demonstrates that FRCN is in charge of most behavioral pattern adjustments in society by disseminating ideas, information, and entertainment to the intended audience.

The radio and television stations are part of Enugu State Broadcasting Services. It has existed in the Eastern region of Nigeria since 1960, when the country gained its independence. Eastern Nigeria Broadcasting Corporation [ENBC] was the previous name of Enugu State Broadcasting Service. The Enugu State Broadcasting Service was founded to efficiently disseminate information throughout the entire state. In 2012, Senator Ike Ekweremmadu, who was the Deputy Senate President at the time, founded Dream FM, 92.5.

In Enugu state, media ownership significantly influences the quality of governance by shaping the information flow to the public. Government-owned media tend to promote the government's agenda, potentially suppressing critical voices and limiting public discourse on important issues. Privately owned media, while potentially more diverse, may prioritize profit or align with specific political or commercial interests, leading to biased reporting and hindering accountability.

Media ownership in Enugu, like in many other places, can significantly impact the quality of governance by shaping public opinion, limiting accountability, and influencing the public's understanding of government actions. A diverse and independent media is essential for promoting transparency, accountability, and good governance. It is against this backdrop that the study examined the influence of media ownership patterns on news content and good governance in Enugu state.

Statement of the Problem

There is no doubt that the media serve as a cornerstone for the promotion of good governance in modern society. This they do by praising politicians when they get it right and criticize them when they get it

wrong. Media outfits owned by politicians or the state government may avoid publishing stories that portray their affiliates in a negative way, and by doing such, there is a clash of interest on the role of the media in promoting good governance.

Government-owned media outlets, like state-owned television or radio stations, often prioritize showcasing government activities and achievements, potentially neglecting critical reporting or analysis of government performance. This study therefore, seeks to assess the influence of media ownership patterns on good governance in Enugu state.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study is to assess the influence of media ownership patterns on good governance in Enugu state. The specific objectives of the study will be to:

1. Ascertain the relationship between media ownership and good governance.
2. Determine the extent to which the media serve as tools for promoting good governance in Enugu state.
3. Examine the relationship between media ownership and media content.
4. Evaluate the relationship between government regulation of the media and good governance.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the relationship between media ownership and good governance?
2. To which extent do the media serve as tools for promoting good governance in Enugu state?
3. What is the relationship between media ownership and media content?
5. What is the relationship between government regulation of the media and good governance?

Literature Review

Mass media refers to technology used as a channel for a small number of people to communicate with a larger number (Hirst, 2018, n.p.). Thus, Madu and Oparaugo (2023) defined the mass media as ‘any device that collects together messages and takes them to a large number of people together at the same time’. When we read newspapers, magazines or books, listen to radio or watch TV we are taking part in mass communication. Iorkase (2013, p.56) posits that the media of mass communication refer to the vehicles or the means by which information or message are conveyed from source to receivers. Mass media are the modern primary means of communicating with large, sometimes instantaneous, disparate, disparate and anonymous audiences (Omeje, Salihu, Oparaugo & Akubulo, 2023, p.44).

The print media started with books. A book is a publication which is bound and covered in either hard or paper back, or in both (Okunna & Omenugha, 2012, p.68). Aniugbo (2016, p.9) posits that print media are light, portable publications printed on paper and distributed as physical copies in the form of books, newspapers, magazines, and newsletters. Iorkase (2013, p.58) further adds that newspaper is one of the basic news medium for majority of the population.

Media ownership is a common concept in journalism studies. It refers to how the media are owned and who are the people who own and control the media. Many authors, (Bagdikian, 2023; Doyle, 2022; Ellis, 2014; Noam, 2016; Shoemaker & Reese, 2013) have suggested that the issue of who owns and controls the media and how much they are allowed to own, matters a lot. Ownership of the media has always revolved around the public and private ownership debate (Forcha & Ngange, 2022). Historically, the state has always monopolised the media landscape before gradually liberalising the sector permitting private ownership which is observed under some strict attribution measures.

Government ownership: Here the government is in charge of the funding of the media organization or has greater control of the shares (Nweze et al., 2019). The funding of the media could be direct funding, loans and overdrafts from banks.

Private ownership: This could also be chain or corporate ownership. The owner or body concerned has a larger share in the funding or it is fully owned by the person or body concerned. For the electronic media since 2012 the National Broadcasting Commission was set up under an Act of the National Assembly No. 38 of 2012 to give licenses to private individuals to own the electronic media.

Co-ownership by Government and Private Persons: It entails the government and private persons sharing proprietary rights over a media establishment. This sort of ownership pattern appears to be scarce in Nigeria, as Omenugha and Uzuegbunam (2015) noted further.

The media in Nigeria faces a complex web of challenges related to ownership and its impact on good governance (Madu & Oparaugo, 2023). While the media is crucial for a functioning democracy, its ability to fulfill its role is often compromised by various forms of control and influence. Overcoming these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach, including strengthening media independence, promoting ethical journalism, and fostering a more engaged and informed citizenry.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on two theories – Social Responsibility theory and Gatekeeping theory.

Social Responsibility theory: This theory can be said to have been initiated in the United States by the Commission of the Freedom of Press, 1947, Eze (2011, pp.83-85). This assertion was supported by Folarin (2002, p.31) when he posited that the theory owes its origin to Hutchinson Commission on Freedom of the Press, set up in the United States of America in 1947 to re-examine the concept of press freedom as emancipated in the Libertarian or free theory.

However, according to Okoro and Agbo (2003, p.23), the major opinion being canvassed by the social responsibility theorists is that the media should fulfill certain obligations and expectations for the society. They went further to say that it is in doing so that the media become socially responsible. Social responsibility theory emphasized that mass media/the press shall have a limited freedom to report issues of public interests. This theory, according to Okoye and Oparaugo (2019), recognises the right of the press to criticise government and institutions and demand also that the press should recognise certain basic responsibilities to maintain the stability of the society, especially national security, peace and order. In applying this theory to this study, the theory argues that the media (whether government-owned or private-owned) should fulfil certain responsibilities in the society. These responsibilities are holding government accountable, criticising government when they do bad and praising them when they do good. In doing this, the media is promoting good governance in Enugu state.

Gatekeeping theory: Gate-keeping theory was propounded by Kurt Lewin. The theory states that there are forces which can either facilitate or constrain the passage of news stories through the gate-keeping process (Shoemaker, 1991).

Gate-keeping refers broadly to the process of controlling information as it moves through a gate or filter and is associated with exercising different types of power (e.g., selecting news, enforcing the status quo in parliamentary committees, mediating between professional and ethnic groups, brokering expert information). This process determines not only which information is selected, but also what the content and nature of messages, such as news and photos will be.

Gate-keeping Theory describes the powerful process through which events are covered by the mass media, explaining how and why certain information either passes through gates or is closed off from media attention. The media, as gate-keepers, decide which news content will be aired on the media. Thus, they control information that passes through their gate. Government-owned media will not air contents on good governance which appear to be attacking the government of the day in a bid to hold power accountable.

Empirical Review

Dogari, Shem and Apuke (2020) studied “Media ownership, funding and challenges: Implication for state owned media survival in Nigeria.” This study examines ownership, funding challenges and its implication for state media survival in Nigeria. The study adopted two research designs- survey and focus group discussion. The participants comprised of 66 registered journalists from Taraba State Broadcasting Service (TSBS) and Taraba Television (TTV). The researchers examined the entire population in order to totally eliminate sampling error. The instruments used for data collection were the questionnaire and the focus group. Sixty-six (66) questionnaires were distributed to the sampled population. Out of the sixty-six (66) questionnaires, sixty-two (62) questionnaires which constitute (94%) were answered correctly by the respondents, while two were not returned and three were not aptly answered hence rendered void. Furthermore, a focus group discussion was conducted on the 5th of November 2017 with six participants from each media station that forms the sampled population. The people who took part in the focus group discussion were reporters and other top management staff. The data collected were analysed both qualitatively and quantitatively. Intrinsically, the data collected through the use of questionnaires were analysed via the 2016 Microsoft statistical package using simple frequency counts and percentage, presented in arithmetic tables. Also, the data collected from the focus group were analysed qualitatively and this involves an in-depth description of the participants’ responses. The findings of this study established that government-owned media in Nigeria are currently in a very poor state economically, managerially, technologically and politically. In addition, misappropriation of the fund, shortage of staff, lack of modern/adequate equipment management, poor salary, inadequate funding and employment of nonprofessionals were discovered to be the major challenges affecting media outfits in Nigeria. In this view, this study suggests that under-funding, which is unfavourable to the operation of state-owned media should be avoided.

Forcha and Ngange (2022) examined “Beyond Public and Private Ownership: Analysis of Media Ownership Patterns in Cameroon and Implications on Journalists’ Professional Aptitude”. This piece of research went beyond already established patterns like public and private to examine salient media ownership patterns within these two grand patterns and to establish the relationship with professionalism in Cameroon. The study made use of a mixed methods approach utilising both qualitative and quantitative analysis. Guided by Altschull’s media ownership theory and the social responsibility theory of Siebert et al., the study found out that beyond private and public media ownership, other salient media ownership patterns exist, such as horizontal ownership (Newspaper 29.3%, Radio 27.9%, TV 11.1%), conglomerate ownership (8.9%) cross ownership (8.1%), sole proprietor ownership(4.3%), vertical ownership (3.3%), religious ownership (2.4%), community ownership (1.4%) regional line ownership (1.1%), political line ownership (0.5%) and co-ownership (0.3%). With this diversified ownership pattern, Cameroon portrays a unique ownership trend similar to those of many African countries but very different from ownership trends in the USA, Europe and other parts of the world where media concentration lies in the hands of one family or a few individuals. Though media concentration is not very visible in Cameroon, some key players in the likes of the Cameroon government (CRTV and SOPECAM), the Groupe l’Anecdote, La Nouvelle Expression, TV+, Spectrum Group, BT Media Group and DASH Media Group are dominating the media landscape in Cameroon. The research established a significant relationship (p -Value = 0.038) between journalists’ professional aptitude and media ownership patterns. However, when it comes to specific media ownership patterns the relationship among these variables varies. Media owners were

found to have an influence on journalists and media content which affects professional aptitude by using various means, including media policy, direct instructions in the editing of news stories, sanctions and orientation of new recruits to the editorial policy of the media house. As a result, basic elements of professional ethics like truth, verification, relevance, balance, fairness and objectivity are compromised in favour of the owner's interests. The study therefore, recommends strict respect for professional norms and canons by both journalists and media owners. Additionally, the government's policy of administrative tolerance on setting up a media organ should be accompanied by strict follow-up measures such as the readiness of such organs to operate in terms of acquiring the necessary equipment, qualified personnel (who will perform their functions freely and objectively) and budget to sustain it.

Njaka and Osi (2023) investigated "Promoting Good Governance through mass media in the South-East Geo-political zone". The research work focuses on promoting good governance through mass media in the SouthEast geo-political zone. A survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study is made up of indigenes of the South-East geo-political zone comprising Anambra, Enugu, Imo, Abia and Ebonyi states. Using simple random sampling techniques, five hundred respondents from political class, civil servants and students were sampled for the study. The instrument for data collection is the questionnaire which has eighteen (18) items designed to elicit information on promoting good governance through mass media in the South-East zone. The instrument was validated by experts in Mass Communication at Federal Polytechnic Oko and experts in Public Administration at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State. The mean statistics was used to analyse the data collected. The findings of the study showed that implications of lack of good governance in the South East are insecurity of lives and property, corruption in public and private sectors, dilapidation of public infrastructures, massive unemployment, abuse of fundamental rights, and electoral frauds among others. It was also discovered that mass media can be used to promote good governance through dissemination of information on government policies, promotion of transparency in government by exposing corrupt practices, dissemination of information on government activities that impede good governance among others. The paper concluded that the media is indispensable in promoting good governance by educating, informing and creating awareness on policies and programmes of the government. Relevant recommendations were made.

Iloмуanya, Umoren, Okalla, Ohiri, Alaekwe and Etumnu (2023) studied "Audience Perception of the Influence of Government Ownership of NTA on Journalism of Truth, Fairness and Balance: A Study of Residents of Owerri Metropolis, Nigeria". The study used a mixed method design, including an in-depth interview for the qualitative data and a survey for the quantitative data. The Wimmer and Dominick online sample size calculator was used to determine a sample size of 384 from the population of 555,500. Data was collected using a questionnaire and interview guide. Multi-stage and purposive sampling procedures were used. The results showed the respondents' high knowledge of the journalistic principles of truth, justice, and balance in news reporting. The respondents have a negative perception towards government ownership of NTA and the practices of the journalists regarding truth, fairness, and balance in news reportage, as the ownership affects the practices of journalists in upholding the principle of truth, fairness, and balance in news reportage. The study further revealed that the respondents perceive that the influence of government control of NTA limits the freedom of the press, which is against the ethics and demands of professional journalism. The paper concluded that when news stories are written and framed in the interest of the owners rather than the public interest, it kills journalistic ethics and professionalism as well as the social responsibility role of the media.

Amos and Joseph (2023) studied Media Ownership and News Coverage: A Critical Appraisal of Private Media Organisation. The study adopted a Library Research approach. Findings revealed that the sorts of owners, ownership structures, and competition in a news market have a considerable impact on how journalism is organized, what it covers, and how it conducts itself in various circumstances.

Ezeugwu (2024) investigated “Ethical Challenges in Journalism Practice: Balancing Media Ownership Interests and Public Responsibility”. This study examines ethical issues in journalism practice and the challenges faced by journalists. It suggests that addressing the challenges stemming from media ownership requires greater press freedom. This would empower reporters and editors in government-owned media organizations to work without fear of reprisal from owners, while also enabling private media owners to operate without the fear of government interference.

Oyinloye et al (2024) examined “Effect of Ownership Pattern on Editorial Contents of Nigerian Newspapers”. This paper examines the influence of media ownership on the gatekeeping role of the media. The paper anchored on the gate keeping theory and propaganda model and review of several literature on the subject matter, and it found out that gate keeping becomes necessary, not only to select the best among billions of stories available, but the economic needs of the medium, organizational policy, owners’ interest, advertisers’ interest, among others, formed criteria for judging/filtering/gatekeeping a particular news story. The paper analyzed the role of gatekeeping/why gate keeping, factors influencing gate keeping, and noted that gate keeping, if not carefully handled, as important as it is for the sanity of the media, may cause untold damage for the integrity of the media. The paper, however, urges the gatekeepers from journalists to the editors, not to allow ownership interest prevent them from discharging social responsibility or sacrifice big human angle stories for the promotion of their proprietors/publishers as this may cause them readership/viewers/listeners’ loyalty.

Methodology

The researcher adopted the survey research method and the descriptive research design for the execution of the study. Survey research method are those researches conducted using the random sampling method to observe and collect data from a large population for the purpose of description, explanation and exploration.

The population of this research work consists the staff of the selected media houses. These staff are journalists, photojournalists, social media managers, public relations officers, reporters, programme hosts/anchors, etc.

FRCN – 240

ESBS – 86

Dream FM – 18

Total – 344

The study adopted the entire population as the sample size owing to its small size. The researcher adopted a census sampling technique of the small and manageable population figure.

Both primary and secondary methods of data were used in this research work for gathering information. Questionnaire was used in gathering data for the study. In treating and analyzing of data collected, extensive use of tabular and percentage were paramount. The data were presented in table and analyzed with SPSS, the hypotheses were tested by the use of Spearman’s Rank Correlation formula.

Data Analysis

Table 1: A significant relationship exists between media ownership and good governance

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	90	31.0	31.0	31.0
Agree	120	41.3	41.3	72.3
Undecided	71	24.5	24.5	96.8
Disagree	3	1.0	1.0	97.8
Strongly Disagree	6	2.4	2.4	100.0
Total	290	100.0	100.0	

The survey shows a significant relationship exists between media ownership and good governance. From the analysis we observe that 90 of them representing 31.0% strongly agreed; 120 representing 41.3% of them agreed; 71 representing 24.5% of them are undecided; 3 representing 1.0% disagreed; while 6 representing 2.4% of them strongly disagreed.

Table 2: Extent to which the media serve as tools for promoting good governance in Enugu state

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid High	100	34.4	34.4	34.4
Average	90	31.0	31.0	65.4
Low	71	24.5	24.5	89.9
Not at all	23	7.9	7.9	97.8
Can't say	6	2.4	2.4	100.0
Total	290	100.0	100.0	

The survey shows the extent to which the media serve as tools for promoting good governance in Enugu state. From the analysis we observe that 100 representing 34.4% of the respondents agreed that to a high extent the media serve as tools for promoting good governance in Enugu state; 90 representing 31.0% of them agreed that to an average extent the media serve as tools for promoting good governance in Enugu state; 71 representing 24.5% of them believed that to a low extent the media serve as tools for promoting good governance in Enugu state; 23 representing 7.9% of them were of the view that the media does not serve as tools for promoting good governance in Enugu state at all, while 6 representing 2.4% of them couldn't say the extent the media serve as tools for promoting good governance in Enugu state.

Table 3: What is the relationship between media ownership and media content

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	24	8.27	8.27	8.72
Agree	49	16.89	16.89	25.61
Undecided	51	17.58	17.58	43.19
Disagree	74	25.51	25.51	68.7
Strongly Disagree	92	31.3	31.3	100.0
Total	290	100.0	100.0	

The survey shows that there is a significant relationship between media ownership and media content. The respondents who strongly agreed to the question were 24 in number given 8.27%; the respondents who agreed were 49 in number given 16.89%; the respondents who were undecided were 51 in number given 17.58%; the respondents who disagreed were 74 in number given 25.51%; the respondents who strongly disagreed were 92 in number given 31.3%.

Table 4: There is a significant relationship between government regulation of the media and good governance

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	90	31.0	31.0	31.0
Agree	120	41.3	41.3	72.3
Undecided	71	24.5	24.5	96.8
Disagree	3	1.0	1.0	97.8
Strongly Disagree	6	2.4	2.4	100.0
Total	290	100.0	100.0	

The survey shows there is a significant relationship between government regulation of the media and good governance. The respondents who strongly agreed that there is a significant relationship between government regulation of the media and good governance were 90 in number given 31.0%; the respondents who agreed that there is a significant relationship between government regulation of the media and good governance were 120 in number given 41.3%; the respondents who were undecided to the question were 71 in number given 24.5%; the respondents who disagreed that there is a significant relationship between government regulation of the media and good governance were 3 in number given 1.0%; the respondents who strongly disagreed that there is a significant relationship between government regulation of the media and good governance were 6 in number given 2.4%.

Discussion of Findings

There is a significant relationship between media ownership and good governance. As in any other clime, the influence of ownership on media operation is absolutely real in Nigeria.

To a high extent, the media serve as tools for promoting good governance in Enugu state. Good governance adds a normative or evaluative attribute to the process of governing. From a human rights perspective, it refers primarily to the process whereby public institutions conduct public affairs, manage public resources and guarantee the realisation of human rights (UNHR, n.d).

There is a significant relationship between media ownership and media content. Ownership of the media has always revolved around the public and private ownership debate (Forcha & Ngange, 2022).

There is a significant relationship between government regulation of the media and good governance. Supporting the above, Nweze, Ario, Nwafor, Nwamba, Aneke, Ekuma, Anyachonkeya, and Chidi-Irem (2019) examined Comparative Analyses of Management of Government and Private Media in South East Nigeria. Findings show that there are in-house policies that guide their day to activities in the media stations.

Conclusion

This study investigated the influence of media ownership patterns on good governance in Enugu state. While recognising the role of the media in enthroning good governance in Enugu state, this study insists that Nigerian media battles with some challenges that clog its wheel in fulfilling its role in enthroning good governance in the society in which it is embedded. One of these challenges is the ownership pattern, politics and pressure. This often leads to dilemmatic media practices, as shown in the exemplars from Nigeria media scene over the years. The onus to achieve this is placed not just on the media themselves, but on the government, the entire Nigerian society and the media practitioners themselves.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher hereby makes the following recommendations:

1. There is need for total press freedom considering the fact that there is a significant relationship between media ownership and good governance.
2. The media should continue serving as tools for promoting good governance, not only in Enugu state, but all over the world.
3. Media houses should continue to produce contents targeted at the promotion of good governance in the society irrespective of ownership.
4. Government of the day should be considerate in its regulation of the media in order not to gag the media against promoting good governance.

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